

D3.2 ENGAGEMENT SERVICES SERVICE UPDATE

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

RDA	Research Data Alliance
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
EOOSC	European Open Science Cloud
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions

Executive summary

This deliverable sets out to report on the RDA Working Group (WG) engagement services that have been carried out to date in the RDA TIGER project. RDA TIGER has started to develop a series of support services to offer the RDA community and a major part of this work is to ensure that the services it creates are optimised for the best user experience, that the candidates of the support services are satisfied and that the support provided is of high-quality and efficient. This report will also provide an overview of work on engagement activities, and some key take-away's moving ahead for the second two years of the project.

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1. Introduction

This short report builds upon the approach and initial concepts outlined in D3.1 to elaborate upon the WP3 engagement approach, and progress to date in engaging and supporting new and existing RDA Working Groups (WGs), and the development of potential future user communities for the landscape and engagement service.

Landscape and engagement activities take place with and on behalf of both existing and prospective WGs; however, such activities to date have occurred primarily at the initial stages of the process of planning and launching a WG. RDA TIGER supports potential WG members to create the group case statement for the RDA Technical Advisory Board (TAB), but also in the later stages once the group is approved and begins the WGs active period.

To receive support from RDA TIGER, including access to the landscape service, the potential WG must prepare a submission in response to an open call issued by RDA TIGER. If successful, this 'pilot group' of proposers is assigned a facilitator. The role of facilitator in RDA TIGER has been to support new WGs following successful applications to the Open Call process in the formulation of their case statement for TAB, and to offer practical assistance in getting the meeting schedule underway for those groups who have been approved by TAB.

The wider remit of WP3 seeks to identify, map and create a resource tool on Open Science issues for RDA WG facilitators and WG members to leverage at different parts of the WG life-cycle. During the timeframe where a potential new group is being formulated, this tool can be used to check for existing initiatives or overlaps within the RDA community and across the wider international Open Science community.

2. Engagement service

The issue the RDA WP3 'Landscape and Engagement' tries to solve for the existing or potential RDA Working Groups (WGs) is the finding and engaging suitable members in these groups, particularly ones which are outside of the "normal" RDA environment. Many of the Working Groups would benefit from a wider membership of experts, and the knowledge of the new WGs could also be useful for the overall research data environment.

The Engagement task is involved in the second part of the landscape and engagement task, i.e. after the landscape analysis has identified the position of the WG in the landscape, and its potential members, the engagement tasks tries to make contact or inform potential participants.

As the landscape and engagement services are optional services for the WGs, they have suffered in the first year for low demand from the pilot WGs. Due to this reason this deliverable mostly describes the main mechanisms attempted and presents the overall pathway for the rest of the project to develop this service further.

As identified in [D3.1](#) "Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets", much effort has been dedicated to engaging relevant networks in order to actively bring membership to the groups, build contact lists and provide suggestions for appropriate co-chairs. WP members leverage their extensive networks among the RDA ecosystem and the wider open science landscape.

Compared to the other RDA TIGER Services (See [D5.1](#) for an overview of the Facilitation Service and [D2.1](#) for the Communications Service), the Landscape Awareness Service has had limited demand, and the focus of the related activities were on developing a database

which will in time be developed into a tool to be used by the WGs. Where WGs did request Landscape services, the facilitator has been the main point of contact.

3. Approaches used to develop Engagement service

The initial plan of the engagement service can be summarised in the following steps:

1. Based on the discussion with (potential) WG members, the initial idea of the types of expertise needed in the WG is identified. Usually this also results in a concrete list of persons to be contacted, and their contact information. This list can also be
2. Additional contact needs can be identified in the landscape analysis (if requested by the WG). This analysis can also identify contact information or specific persons to contact.
3. The actual engagement happens via one of the following mechanisms:
 - a. Wide dissemination of the WG to the communities in question (e.g. in RDA or to specific domain group)
 - b. Specific engagement with identified individuals. This can be done either by the RDA TIGER staff or via the WG members directly.
4. Additional engagement actions can be needed to convince WG members to take organisational role in the WG, particularly for the role of co-chairs.

3.1 Information collection

Under task 3.1 (Open Science landscape monitoring and engagement baseline, lead by CODATA), the RDA TIGER team works on creating and maintaining the generic body-of-knowledge on major international open science initiatives. Using the extensive networks of the collaborating organisations, the aim is to build a resource that supports robust and active interaction with all stakeholders both at an EOSC level and globally. The monthly meetings in *WP5 Facilitation* discuss each potential WG individually and make decisions on appropriate knowledge among consortium members. This information is shared with WP3, mostly via the same staff members being part of the both WPs.

The WP3 together with the facilitator service (WP5) dedicates time to scanning the landscape for relevant initiatives and individuals and compiling a list. This work will also draw heavily on [D3.1](#)¹. All relevant areas will be explored. One example is checking the EOSC Working Groups for relevant outputs or consortium partners, such as CODATA's Task Groups and Working Groups. The list being developed at this stage will be a reference point later in the WG as the outputs are developed.

Holding a first virtual kick-off meeting

WG kick-off meetings are a key milestone in the WG before the case-statement is submitted. These meetings engage at a group setting with the membership and potential co-chairs identified during earlier stages of this service, help define and solidify the groups' aims, plans and planned outputs, provide a solid starting point for the collaborative efforts of an RDA WG, and form the basis of the relationship between the RDA TIGER facilitator and the WG.

Creating a Contacts List

A contacts list with potential membership, co-chairs, stakeholders and target audiences is collated in collaboration with the Communication Service and as part of the groups'

¹ Rettberg, N., Asmi, A., Molloy, L., Hugo, W., Delipalta, A., & Saldner, S. (2023)

communication plan, and forms a concrete output and an important asset to the groups. It is constantly updated and stored in an accessible place for all group members to access and add to. At the virtual kick-off meetings, emails are collected, with appropriate GDPR permissions. This list is used initially to engage with potential membership as the groups form, and at later stages for output dissemination and stakeholder engagement.

Key experiences and development ideas

- 1) The use of the initiating groups' own information channels is crucial for contact lists, but one needs to avoid biases from very specific group specialities and backgrounds. Combination of both RDA and domain specific knowledge seems to produce more diverse groups. Special attention should be paid more in the geographical diversity also outside of the developed world. Use of TAB more in the connection searching is crucial. Overall information collection could also be more widely distributed, e.g. by crowdsourcing within the RDA community if possible.
- 2) In the landscape analysis, identifying similar RDA historical outputs lead to many potential interested communities and other leads of potential contacts.
- 3) Use of existing databases should be further used in this step. As an example, a recent landscape analysis brought up a very comprehensive database of repositories called OpenDOAR, which provided immediate knowledge of such repositories usable by the WG which would have been extremely hard to collect directly.
- 4) The service should be made clear as a primary step in setting up a WG, before the case statement is created in terms of identifying potential group members. The team should advocate for the use of the Engagement service by the groups to support the growth of the group, diversity and a global perspective.

3.2 Engagement

Direct contacting via electronic means

The WGs were widely advertised in the RDA channels to the whole community available via these mailing lists. Additionally, the contact lists and other community email lists were used in to get non-RDA members involved. Similar directed contacts were used by the RDA TIGER employees and the relevant active WG members to contact potential membership.

Key experiences and development ideas

- 1) Use of email templates was successful, and they can also give additional information for the recipients not so familiar with the RDA WG process. However, the types of the information provided this far seem to need improvement and more user-targeted means are needed. Emails coming from the RDA TIGER team need to be adjusted in the specific WG needs and to the recipient type and their priorities.
- 2) Special attention should be made to make clear the required work load of the WG members (not necessarily high, but could lead to more activities).
- 3) There is a need to create "information package" of each supported WG, with one page directed to the main WG goals from the perspective of the target audience, and the other one more describing the overall processes of the RDA WG and co-chairs' role.

Physical meetings / RDA Plenaries

Two different physical meetings were used for engagement in this period. EOSC Symposium and RDA Plenaries.

Plenaries are vital networking opportunities for all the RDA TIGER WGs. These events are integral to the groups' working plans, and discussions to hold plenary working sessions are part of the planning carried out between facilitators and WG from the very start. Having these face to face meetings with the community is critical (while also accommodating hybrid and virtual participation) in order to kick-start the groups' work or to implement the WG actions, and support outreach opportunities to the wider global RDA membership. Throughout this deliverable the plenaries are often referred to as P20, P21 (as part of International Data Week 2023) and P22. These are the previous and future plenaries coordinated by RDA. The meetings included direct workshops organised by the RDA WGs and more general plenary sessions as well as a poster session and RDA TIGER specific booth.

Similar activity was done in the EOSC Symposium, Madrid (September, 2023), but more towards creation of new RDA TIGER WGs and to inform target audiences for the potentially interesting RDA TIGER WGs. Special attention was done on the overall visibility of the RDA, and the global collaboration plenary was coordinated by the RDA TIGER project.

Key experiences and development ideas

- 1) Ensure WG are present in the RDA Plenary programmes and that sessions are held at the upcoming Plenaries, e.g timely submissions and session descriptions. The WGs should be very visibly promoted.
- 2) Use of personal contacts and engaging in other sessions is crucial, as they can identify key people to involve in the RDA WGs. This is specially important for non-RDA plenaries.
- 3) Available material needs to be targeted to the participants of the meeting, and inclusion of special material (e.g. videos, etc) usable for that audience in particular is very useful. Use of the advertisement template on the presentations can lead to more engagement.

3.3. Identifying WG co-chairs

Identifying co-chairs and ensuring diversity is one of the priorities of all WGs. Co-chairs play a special role in initialising a group and formulating the concept and aims of the group². An RDA group needs co-chairs from different parts of the world to ensure a truly global approach and perspective to the challenges addressed. The RDA TIGER engagement service provides recommendations for co-chairs by identifying candidates from personal and organisational contacts and the wider RDA network.

Key experiences and development ideas

- 1) Highlight the benefits of being a co-chair, include information on the RDA TIGER support mechanisms lowering the effort needed, be inclusive in the co-chair suggestions (e.g. towards more junior WG members).

4. Group feedback and service improvement

Part of the engagement tasks is to improve the service design and delivery by considering feedback received from the supported groups. Overall, the supported groups value the

² See more here <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/creating-and-managing-rda-groups/rda-group-chairs-roles-and-responsibilities>

services provided by the facilitator, with some particularly appreciating the deep contextual knowledge of the facilitator and their ability to navigate the RDA's processes. The feedback we have encountered so far on the Engagement services from the anonymous form:

A comment from the form also flagged up the engagement work on behalf of the facilitator as being very useful, especially *“processing information from different sources to pre-populate case statement”* - Comment on the Feedback form 13.9.23

“Our working group receives support in organising meetings and connecting stakeholders. The facilitators have identified opportunities for events to help progress our work. Our facilitators have domain expertise to provide meaningful support for our workgroup questions.” From an interview on PROARs group 28.11.23

Key experiences and development ideas

- 1) The success of the Engagement service should be followed by changes in the of group active membership Maintain records of number of new members over time.
- 2) As efforts to date have focused on compiling a landscape database and providing ad-hoc support to the groups that requested landscape and engagement services, the next step is for the main service offerings to be outlined into concrete service 'packages'. The service can then be more formally offered to interested groups and carried out in well-defined steps.

